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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: May 2014

Katie Frey Updated on August 24, 2022 [Leave a Comment](#)

Visual Astronomy Display for May 2014

Highlights...

- We have several videos about the recent lunar eclipse, including a **time lapse video of the blood moon**;
- Science@NASA presents us with a **real life example of Einstein's twin paradox**, describing the various studies that will be taken as one twin orbits the Earth for a year and one stays behind on the planet;
- Dr. Don Lincoln from **Fermilab explains dark energy**, talking about the observations that lead to it's discovery and current research on the subject;
- The **LADEE mission comes to a close**, successfully completing a planned de-orbit and crashing into the surface of the moon.

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Bonus Videos...

- A [three part series](#) on how to **build a Dobsonian telescope** from the BBC Sky and Night Magazine.

[Playlist Archive Suggestions, Comments, or Questions](#)

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Katie Frey

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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